

Virtual environment program for learning scientific inquiry in students of an educational institution

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Abstract— The present study aims to develop and evaluate a virtual environment program for scientific inquiry learning among students at an educational institution, in 2024. The Sustainable Development Goal considered was No. 4 on Quality Education. The study's methodology used a quantitative, applied approach and a quasi-experimental design. The control population consisted of 150 first-year students, consisting of 21 first-year C students, and the experimental population consisted of 21 first-year A students. A survey technique was used, and the selected instrument consisted of a knowledge test. The Kuder-Richardson test was used for reliability assessment, and the result was 0.870, interpreted as high reliability. The conclusion was that the virtual environment program has a significant influence on students' scientific inquiry learning; $p = 0.000$ indicates that the implementation of the program, which considered virtual environments, significantly improved students' scientific inquiry skills.

Keywords: Virtual environments, research, identification, dissemination

I. INTRODUCTION

It was also considered that this research was important due to the need to enhance scientific inquiry. Access to virtual learning environments focused on scientific investigation is one of the key pillars for promoting digital literacy. Based on this, the concern arose to develop a virtual environment program aimed at fostering scientific inquiry among students. In this context, the study was grounded in Sustainable Development Goal No. 4: Quality Education (United Nations [UN], 2024).

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2023), only one-third of students across 12 educational systems had access to simulation software. Class recordings have proven useful for identifying and correcting deficiencies in teaching quality. In China, for instance, recorded lessons improved Chinese language skills by 32% among rural students. However, in Peru, the distribution of laptops did not enhance learning outcomes due to insufficient attention to their pedagogical integration. In India, students showed improved performance in out-of-school learning environments, whereas in the United States, the use of artificial intelligence did not outperform traditional teaching methods. Globally, 54% of countries have established digital competence standards for students, and the European Commission has defined five key areas within this framework. Nonetheless, some nations have approached digital skills from a commercial standpoint, thereby deepening inequality. In the European Union, 54% of adults had at least basic digital competence in 2021, while in Brazil, digital proficiency was significantly higher in urban areas and among higher socioeconomic groups.

In Latin American countries, faced challenges in the use of virtual learning environments. This helped reduce educational disparities among students while also encouraging the use of ICT within families, who in turn developed digital skills through the use of educational technology.

In Ecuador, a project was implemented to assess students' levels of digital literacy. The findings revealed a significant lack of technological knowledge among students, with only a small portion demonstrating basic digital competencies. This situation posed challenges for both teachers and learners, leading to the adoption of distance education and nationwide radio-based learning programs designed according to educational levels. Another important resource consisted of printed pedagogical guides distributed to households with limited internet access, while various digital platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, Zoom, and WhatsApp were used to facilitate learning. These initiatives brought substantial changes within families,

who became more actively involved in the teaching–learning process by using educational technologies and providing support to their children in managing these tools (Calle et al., 2022).

In Colombia, with a population of approximately 51.07 million, it was revealed that 80% of citizens live in urban areas, where access to devices such as mobile phones, tablets, and laptops exceeds the total population, reaching a connectivity rate of around 119%. During the quarantine period, the demand for internet connectivity and the use of social networks increased significantly, serving as tools for maintaining contact with family and friends, as well as for educational and scientific inquiry purposes across primary, secondary, vocational, and higher education levels. These digital interactions have contributed to the development of cognitive and logical thinking skills, enabling students to investigate, experiment, and achieve successful outcomes. The influence of natural sciences has become increasingly evident within the sociocultural context, while technological advancements continue to play a key role in improving the quality of life and social development (Alvino, 2021).

In this regard, the main research question is stated as follows: What is the impact of the virtual learning environment program on the scientific inquiry learning of students at an educational institution in Breña in 2024? The main objective was to assess the impact of the virtual learning environment program on the scientific inquiry learning of students at an educational institution in Breña in 2024.

In international studies, Canchola et al. (2023) conducted research evaluating the impact of remote laboratories as a teaching tool for improving knowledge, skills, and attitudes, as well as enhancing scientific literacy within the telesecundaria context. A mixed-method approach was applied, using a quasi-experimental pretest–posttest design. The participants consisted of 21 second-grade secondary students. The main findings revealed that remote laboratories positively contributed to students' scientific understanding. The study concluded that the ease of use and relevance of these tools promote the collection of experimental evidence through direct interaction with natural phenomena. Although electronic laboratories cannot fully replace traditional ones, their implementation enables the creation of accessible and manageable school laboratories, making them particularly beneficial in educational settings with limited resources.

Cascarosa and Pozuelo (2024) carried out a study aimed at fostering scientific inquiry through a guided inquiry approach. Using a quantitative experimental design, they developed a learning sequence involving a weather station to promote scientific competence through structured guidance. Two specific rubrics were applied to analyze data collected from audio and video recordings. The results indicated that this sequence effectively enhanced students' scientific competence, improving their ability to design and analyze research as well as their procedural and epistemic understanding.

Meneses et al. (2024) conducted a study aimed at examining the impact of the usability of *IndagApp*, an ICT-based tool designed to support science education by providing information to students. Using a mixed-methods approach and a panel of 14 experts, the quantitative findings indicated high usability, while the qualitative results led to improvements in the interface and curricular alignment. The final version of *IndagApp* features ten curriculum-based activities and includes support materials for both teachers and students. This innovative tool contributes to enhancing science education across Ibero-America, and future research will explore its application in primary and secondary education settings.

Jones and Sturrock (2021) found that structured active learning proved more effective than the traditional flipped classroom approach, as it promoted greater engagement and participation. Students in the virtual environment and tutoring sessions were able to contribute to their final assessment, accounting for up to 10% of the module credit. Continuous feedback was provided through rubrics, with over 90% of students accessing the materials, and participation in learning activities significantly increased under the active learning approach—from 40% to 78%.

Petegem & Jolie (2024) conducted a study aimed at identifying the use of virtual environments—particularly online collaborative work—in enhancing scientific inquiry. Using a quantitative approach and a quasi-experimental design with a sample of 1,611 students, the results showed that the Norwegian version of the scale was a valid and reliable instrument for measuring sociability in self-organized student project contexts. The study concluded that the use of virtual learning environments, especially for online collaboration, effectively supports the improvement of scientific inquiry skills.

Nazempour (2023) conducted a study to evaluate the impact of methods for personalizing educational resources in virtual environments with the goal of improving academic performance. Using a quantitative methodology and an experimental design, the research analyzed students' interactions with learning management systems to understand their behavior. The results combined learning style data with demographic information to train models capable of predicting students' academic performance each term. From this, the study identified style characteristics that increased pass rates, revealing that students whose learning styles aligned with the predictive models achieved higher grades. The research concluded that virtual strategies had a significant positive effect on scientific inquiry.

Evangelista (2021) conducted a study aimed at identifying the effect of hybrid learning on scientific inquiry. The research followed a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental design. The findings revealed that ensemble methods achieved higher accuracy in prediction compared to individual classifiers, and that overall precision improved through the use of feature selection techniques. In conclusion, the virtual learning strategy enhanced students' scientific inquiry skills.

Rodríguez et al. (2020) conducted a study aimed at determining the effect of specific strategies designed to enhance students' scientific inquiry skills. The research followed a quantitative, experimental methodology and was implemented through three mathematics and science workshops, while two additional sessions involved a questionnaire based on PISA-related problems. The results revealed a gap between the information provided in the problems and the students' effective responses. The study concluded that students tended to use authentic problem-solving procedures when the statements did not specify a particular method for addressing them.

From a methodological standpoint, the justification lies in the fact that the project introduces an innovative method aimed at producing valid and reliable knowledge. The study seeks to discover new methods or techniques for generating knowledge, or to explore alternative ways of conducting research; therefore, it can be stated that it holds a methodological justification (Mendez, 2000). Methodologically, the study provided tools that have been validated and proven to be reliable.

The theoretical foundation of the virtual learning environments program was based on Siemens' Digital Constructivism Theory, also known as *Connectivism*. This approach suggests that learning in the digital age is not merely an individual process of acquiring knowledge but also involves connecting ideas, information sources, and people through digital networks. According to Siemens (2005), the key principles of this theory emphasize that knowledge functions as a network—no longer a static entity transmitted from one person to another, but something constructed within a system that integrates information, technologies, and human connections. Connectivism asserts that learning must adapt to the continuous flow and transformation of information. Decision-making and critical judgment play an essential role in maintaining the continuous interaction between technology and learning (Zhao et al., 2017). Furthermore, social and collective learning highlight that knowledge creation does not occur solely at an individual level; rather, connections enable access to new information and the generation of knowledge in a more efficient and dynamic way (Best et al., 2024).

Active learning is implemented through sequential activities, allowing students to move between processes in various ways (Hartikainen et al., 2019). Therefore, the use of evaluative exercises combined with feedback promotes the development of inquiry-based competencies (Teixeira de Sousa et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the theory of convergence culture explains how digital technologies have transformed media interaction and communication. Some of its most relevant dimensions include: Media Convergence, which refers to the integration and fusion of different media platforms and formats, allowing content to flow across multiple channels (television, internet, cinema, etc.); Participation, where media consumers become active creators involved in producing, distributing, and consuming content—such as through fan fiction, blogs, and videos; Participatory Culture, highlighting the growing importance of online communities and social networks where individuals collaborate, share, and co-create knowledge; Transmedia, a storytelling approach that unfolds across multiple platforms, with each medium offering a unique contribution to the overall narrative; Collective Intelligence, which emphasizes the distributed and shared nature of knowledge that enhances creativity and problem-solving; and Audience Diversity, recognizing that people consume and produce content differently, influenced by their cultural and social contexts (Jenkins, 2008).

The strategies implemented relied on active methodologies, which enable the development of investigative practices in education (Abreu, 2019). In this sense, learning is a dynamic process—knowledge is not static but constantly evolving and expanding, particularly due to technological advances (Aldahdouh, 2020). Teachers play a crucial role in designing learning strategies and fostering the scientific training students need (Mirabal & Caballero, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to strengthen teachers' research skills (Orama et al., 2021), including the development of digital competencies and scientific production to ensure meaningful student learning (Rodríguez et al., 2019). Consequently, it is recommended that teacher training be self-managed and focused on socio-scientific approaches (Lorenzo et al., 2025).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. *Design*

The design of this research had an experimental design of the quasi-experimental subtype, which included the administration of pretests to the groups participating in the experiment. Participants were randomly assigned to each group, and both received the pretest simultaneously. One group was exposed to the experimental treatment, while the control group did not receive it. Finally, a posttest was administered concurrently to both groups (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

2.2. *Participants*

The population was consisted of all the elements (units of analysis) within the geographical area or context of the study (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018). It represents an objective and representative section that accurately reflects the characteristics of the whole, allowing the findings to be generalized to the entire population. The study population included 150 first-year students. The inclusion criteria considered were first-year students whose parents provided informed consent. The exclusion criteria included students with irregular attendance and those whose parents did not authorize their participation.

2.3. *Measuring instruments*

For this research the survey technique was employed to collect information through measurement instruments specifically designed to obtain data related to the study variable. Such an instrument must meet essential criteria such as objectivity, validity, and reliability (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018). The applied technique was the survey, and the selected instrument consisted of a knowledge test.

2.4. Procedure

The procedure descriptive analyses were conducted to summarize the results of the variables and their dimensions. To test the hypothesis, a normality test was first performed to determine the appropriate statistical method. Since the data did not follow a normal distribution, the nonparametric Mann–Whitney U test was applied.

III.RESULTS

TABLE I
ACHIEVED THE INQUIRY PROFICIENCY LEVEL

Level	Control Group				Experimental Group			
	Pretest		postest		Pretest		postest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	21	100	21	100	21	100	2	9.5
Process	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	76.2
Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	14.3
Total	21	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0

In the qualitative analysis Table 1 shows that, in the pretest phase, both groups obtained identical results. However, in the posttest, the control group exhibited 100% at the initial level, while the experimental group showed 9.5% at the initial level, 76.2% in progress, and 14.3% achieved the inquiry proficiency level.

TABLE 2
RESULT OF IDENTIFYING THE PROBLEMS

Level	Control Group				Experimental Group			
	postest		Pretest		postest		Pretest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	20	95.2	20	95.2	20	95.2	6	28.6
Process	1	4.8	1	4.8	1	4.8	8	38.1
Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	33.3
Total	21	100.0	22	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0

Table 2 indicates that, in the pretest stage, both groups obtained identical results. However, in the posttest, the control group showed 95.2% at the initial level and 4.8% in progress, while the experimental group recorded 28.6% at the initial level, 38.1% in progress, and 33.3% achieved the proficiency level in identifying inquiry problems.

TABLE 3
Result of generation

Level	Control Group				Experimental Group			
	posttest		Pretest		posttest		Pretest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	21	100	17	81.0	19	90.5	1	4.8
Process	0	0	4	19.0	2	9.5	16	76.2
Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	19.0
Total	21	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0

Table 3 shows that, in the pretest stage, both groups obtained similar results. In the posttest, the control group displayed 81% at the initial level and 19% in progress, while the experimental group recorded 4.8% at the initial level, 76.2% in progress, and 19% achieved the proficiency level in data generation during inquiry.

TABLE 4
Result of dissemination of inquiry

Level	Control Group				Experimental Group			
	posttest		Pretest		posttest		Pretest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	5	23.8	3	14.3	9	42.9	0	0
Process	15	71.4	14	66.7	12	57.1	2	9.5
Achievement	1	4.8	4	19.0	0	0	19	90.5
Total	21	100.0	22	100.0	21	100.0	21	100.0

Table 4 shows that, in the pretest phase, both groups obtained similar results, with most students at the initial level. In the posttest, the control group showed 14.3% at the initial level, 66.7% in progress, and 19% achieving the expected level of mastery. In contrast, the experimental group reported 9.5% in progress and 90.5% reaching the achievement level in the dissemination of inquiry.

TABLE 5
Result of central tendency measure of the pre- and post-test of the experimental group

	N	Mín	Máy	Media	Desv.
Learning Scientific Inquiry (Pre-test)	21	1,00	6,00	4,43	1,39898
Learning Scientific Inquiry (Post-test)	21	6,00	15,00	11,43	2,31455
Problem Identification (Pre-test)	21	,00	2,00	,57	,59761
Problem Identification (Post-test)	21	,00	3,00	2,00	,89443
Pre-test Generation	21	,00	4,00	2,24	,99523
Post-test Generation	21	3,00	8,00	5,10	1,30018
Dissemination (Pre-test)	21	,00	3,00	1,62	,97346
Dissemination (Post-test)	21	2,00	5,00	4,33	,79582

Table 5 shows that the average score for scientific inquiry learning in the pretest was 4.43, increasing to 11.43 in the posttest. For the dimensions, problem identification scored 0.57 in the pretest and 2 in the posttest; data generation scored 2.24 in the pretest and 5.10 in the posttest; and dissemination scored 1.62 in the pretest and 4.33 in the posttest. These results indicate a considerable improvement after the intervention.

TABLE 6
NORMAL TEST

	Kolmogórov-Smirnov		
	Estadístico	gl	Sig.
Learning Scientific Inquiry (Pre-test)	,217	42	,000
Learning Scientific Inquiry (Post-test)	,366	42	,000
Problem Identification (Pre-test)	,263	42	,000
Problem Identification (Post-test)	,200	42	,000
Pre-test Generation	,147	42	,021
Post-test Generation	,235	42	,000
Dissemination (Pre-test)	,127	42	,077
Dissemination (Post-test)	,216	42	,000

In the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, it was found that the variable scientific inquiry learning and nearly all of its dimensions showed a significance level lower than 0.05. Therefore, it was determined that a nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test should be applied to test the hypotheses, allowing for the comparison between different groups.

TABLE 7
CONTRASTS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP LEARNING OF SCIENTIFIC INQUIRY IN PRE AND POST-TESTS

Estadístico de prueba^a		
	Scientific inquiry pre test	Scientific inquiry pos test
U de Mann-Whitney	214,000	15,500
W de Wilcoxon	467,000	268,500
Z	-,424	-5,270
Sig. asintótica(bilateral)	,672	,000

a. Variable de agrupación: Grupo

In the general hypothesis test, it was found that in the pretest, $p = 0.672$, whereas in the posttest, the p -value = 0.000, indicating significant differences in the experimental group. This demonstrates that the virtual learning environments program effectively enhances students' scientific inquiry learning in an educational

institution. Furthermore, in the posttest, the z-value = -5.270; since this value is greater than the critical value of -1.96, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the study's alternative hypothesis is accepted.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show consistent with those of Canchola et al. (2023), who state that remote laboratories, as a didactic tool, enhance students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, as well as their development of scientific literacy within the telesecundaria context. Remote labs contribute to scientific learning by facilitating the collection of experimental evidence through interaction with natural phenomena. Although electronic laboratories cannot fully replace traditional ones, their use enables the creation of accessible and easy-to-manage school laboratories. Therefore, their integration is particularly valuable in educational settings with limited resources.

Similarly, Petegem and Sjolie (2024) concluded that the use of virtual learning environments, particularly for online collaborative work, enhances scientific inquiry. In addition, Nazempour (2023) found that applying methods to personalize educational resources in virtual settings helps improve academic performance. These learning styles were combined with demographic data to train models that predict students' academic outcomes. From this, it was identified that certain style characteristics increase success rates, and students whose learning styles aligned with the model's predictions achieved higher grades. Therefore, it was concluded that virtual strategies have a significant positive effect on scientific inquiry.

Likewise, Meneses et al. (2024) reported similar findings, identifying the impact of the usability of IndagApp, an ICT tool designed to teach science through interactive information for students. This innovative resource supports science education across Ibero-America, and future studies will examine its application in primary and secondary education.

The virtual environment program is supported by the study of Bullón et al. (2024), who found a correlation between digital competencies and attitudes toward the use of ICTs. The study highlights the importance of these elements in improving educational quality, particularly within the context of the health emergency.

The results are supported by Kolb's experiential learning theory, which is based on a model explaining how individuals acquire knowledge through their experiences. This model consists of four key stages: Concrete Experience, which involves direct engagement in an activity or situation; Reflective Observation, where individuals reflect on what happened and why; Abstract Conceptualization, during which learners develop theories and concepts from their reflections; and Active Experimentation, where the acquired knowledge is applied in new contexts, leading to further experiences (Gómez, 2008). For instance, project-based learning strategies that integrate technological resources promote cooperative learning among teachers (Añazco, 2024).

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the general objective, it was concluded that the virtual learning environments program had a significant influence on students' scientific inquiry learning, as the value of $p = 0.000$ indicates that, after implementing the program based on virtual environments, students' scientific inquiry skills improved significantly.

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